

INFO SECURE SYSTEM USING MACHINE LEARNING

Mr.D.Vimal kumar ^{#1}, E.Dhanasekar ^{#2}, S.Selva prakesh ^{#3}, R.Selva kumar ^{#4}, M.Rajesh ^{#5}

^{1#} Assistant Professor, Information Technology, Hindustan Institute of Technology, Coimbatore
^{2, 3, 4, 5#} Student, Information Technology, Hindustan Institute of Technology, Coimbatore

Abstract: The term cyber security is often employed interchangeably with the term protection of information. Cyber security and information protection are significantly similar, these two terms are not completely comparable. In addition, the paper argues that cyber security stretches beyond conventional information security definitions to include not only the protection of information data, but also that of other properties, including the individual himself. In information protection, reference to the human factor is generally linked to human's role(s) in the process of protection. In cyber security this aspect has a further element, namely, humans as possible targets of cyber-attacks or even engaging unknowingly in a cyber-assault. This additional aspect has ethical consequences for society as a whole, as it may be seen as a social obligation to protect such marginalized groups, for example children.

Keywords: Information security, Cyber security, Cyber security, Cyber-Security, Computer security, Risk, Threat, Vulnerability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Cyber security has developed into a topic of global significance and value. More than 50 countries have already officially published some form of strategy paper outlining their official stance on cyberspace, cybercrime and/or cyber security. Cyber security is used, in most literature, as an all-inclusive term. Definitions of this word differ, e.g. the Merriam Webster dictionary defines it as "measures taken to protect a device or computer network from unauthorized access or attack" The International Telecommunications Union (ITU) describes the following for cyber security. Cybersecurity is the array of resources, procedures, security principles, safety protocols, rules, risk management strategies, activities, training, best practices, compliance, and technology that can be used to secure the cyber environment and the properties of the company and user. Assets of the organization and user include connected computing devices, staff, equipment, software, utilities, telecommunications networks, and the entirety of information exchanged and/or processed in the cyber world.

Cyber security seeks to ensure that the security resources of the company and the assets of users are obtained and protected against specific physical threats in the cyber world. The general safety targets include the following: Availability, Integrity, which may include authenticity and nonrepudiation, Confidentiality. Those meanings are somewhat similar to information security concepts. This paper would discuss in detail the meaning of information security and then suggest that in terms of how it is traditionally defined, the limits of cyber security as a concept are broader than those of information protection. This paper will concentrate primarily on the fundamental nature of security in general and seek to illustrate, through examples that the purpose of cybersecurity assets is to protect an additional dimension that stretches beyond traditional information security boundaries. This paper further argues that all human beings in their personal capacity and society as a whole may be directly harmed or influenced by cyber-security attacks, although this is not generally the case for information security where harm is often indirect. This disambiguation is seen by the authors as a significant addition to the popular body of information and cyber security expertise for the field. Such a body of information in the subject field offers a "foundation for interpreting words and concepts" and thus serves as a "taxonomy of topics applicable to practitioners around the world."

According to Whitman and Mattord, the industry standard has historically been to ensure the confidentiality, honesty and availability of information, which is also known as the CIA triangle of information security. "The security of these three information characteristics is as important today as it has always been, but the CIA triangle model no longer adequately addresses the computer industry's ever-changing climate". A few terms in the descriptions above need to be explored in greater depth. Firstly, it should be clear that the protection of information is not a software or technology but a process. Safety of information according to Wood used to be a purely technical problem. However, as the use of computers and networks grew, the securing method for these computers and networks also had to change in order to expand beyond just the technological.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Knowing and being ready is the first line of protection against cyber threats and cybercrimes, e.g. by information security training. Training can take two forms, the first is aimed at security professionals and aims to improve understanding of the latest threats and to increase skill levels in defending and mitigating against them. [1]. In this review, we establish a taxonomy for cyber range systems and analyze existing literature that focuses on architecture and scenarios, but also capacities, functions, resources etc. In this paper the IoT-based smart grid's risks and future approaches are analysed and focus on forms of cyber threats and include an in-depth of the smart grid's cyber-security environment. In particular, we concentrate on addressing and analyzing vulnerabilities in

the network, challenging countermeasures, and requiring protection. We strive to provide a deep understanding of cyber-security vulnerabilities and solutions, and provide a roadmap to future cyber-security research directions in smart grid applications [2].

A cyber security control V&V process model is built in this study to solve the problem, based on the principle of adaptive focusing testing. Additionally a quantitative approach is built to define and prioritize fault-prone information security controls. It has been verified that the model built may provide an additional and more reliable framework for expert subjective judgment [3]. This article focus on the importance of different cyber defense standards, and cyber security framework architecture. We discuss security threats, assaults and cyber security measures. Then we discuss the different issues of standardization of cyber security. We also address the national information security policy to secure cyberspace, as well as various government strategies in protecting cyber security. Finally, we have some important guidelines for information security and informationsafety [4]. This paper discusses the requirements required for the Federal Government's evaluation of cybersecurity policies for the United States Department of Health and Human Services.

The overarching aim of cyber security policies and procedures is enabled by compliance with established Federal regulations and standards to protect the operational resources and goals of the United States Department of Health and Human Resources and to encourage best practices of security in the defense of information systems against unauthorized actors and cyber threats [5]. This automation reduces human errors in order processing, and increases order delivery performance. However, attacks from cyberspace, particularly from the Internet, can disrupt that. In this paper, we propose a novel attacker-defender model against an adversary of the quantum response (QR) to protect critical assets by considering the defending budget and the reliance on properties. The protection level of each asset in the solution indicates its desirability to be secured [6]. This paper present a survey of deep learning approaches for detecting cyber security attack, the datasets used, and a comparative analysis.

In particular, we provide an overview of intrusion detection systems focused on deep learning approaches. The dataset plays an important role in intrusion detection, so we define 35 well-known cyber datasets and group such datasets into seven categories: network traffic dataset, electric network dataset, internet traffic dataset, virtual private network dataset, android device dataset, IoT traffic dataset, and internet link [7]. Machine learning techniques are commonly used in the creation of an intrusion detection system (IDS) for the timely and automated detection and classification of cyberattacks at network and host rates. However, when malicious attacks are continuously evolving and occur in very large quantities requiring a scalable solution, several problems come up. There are numerous databases of malware publicly accessible for further study by the information security community [8].

The ultimate goal of this study is to automatically and efficiently learn useful feature representations from large quantities of unlabeled raw network traffic data by using deep learning approaches. We propose a novel intrusion model for the network by stacking dilated convolutionary auto encoders and testing our approach on two new datasets for intrusion detection. Several studies have been carried out to test that our method is successful [9]. First we present the general technique of deep learning and its theoretical consequences for the issue of network intrusion detection. We then analyze several machine learning solutions for two tasks of network intrusion detection [10]

III. METHODOLOGY

DATA ENCRYPTION FROM ONE TO ANOTHER IP

A. Encryption

The encryption of an IP address involves the application of encryption methods to conceal the true IP address when it is sent or saved. This can increase privacy and security, but it is not a typical practice for standard IP address communication. In certain scenarios, technologies like Virtual Private Networks (VPNs) or proxy servers can be utilized to obscure the original IP address, providing a form of encryption for data related to IP addresses.

Encryption is a method of utilizing algorithms to convert data into a secure format that obstructs unauthorized access. It aids in safeguarding delicate details while it is being sent or stored. Encryption can be extremely helpful in reducing the damage caused by a system compromise. Even if unwanted parties access sensitive data, well designed encryption can keep it secure. It's crucial to remember that encryption does not, by itself, stop hacking; rather, it lessens the damage by rendering the stolen data unintelligible without the decryption key. A mix of strong security techniques, such as frequent updates, strong authentication, intrusion detection, and encryption, is necessary to effectively guard against hacking.

B. Encryption with AI

Using artificial intelligence to secure sensitive information using encryption processes is known as "encryption with AI." AI can be used in a number of encryption-related processes, such as key creation, secure communication protocols, and vulnerability analysis. The generation of encryption keys is one way that AI is used in encryption. Strong and random encryption keys, which are necessary for guaranteeing the security of encrypted data, can be generated using machine learning algorithms under the right conditions. By analysing patterns, AI may create keys that are challenging to brute-force or guess.

AI can also be used to improve communication protocols like transport layer security (TLS) and the secure socket layer (SSL). Real-time network traffic monitoring, anomaly detection, and potential threat or attack identification are all capabilities of AI algorithms. This enables the system to react and enhance the security of encrypted communication by changing encryption algorithms or preventing questionable activity.

AI can also assist in vulnerability assessments by identifying potential flaws in protocols and encryption techniques. AI algorithms can find holes or vulnerabilities through in-depth analysis and testing that may be challenging for traditional approaches to find. These flaws can be discovered in order to improve encryption technology and lessen security risks. By creating robust encryption keys, enhancing communication protocols, and spotting weaknesses, sensitive data may be kept secure.

In order to increase security and efficiency, encryption with AI refers to the application of artificial intelligence (AI) methods and procedures.

Traditionally, encryption entails employing cryptographic techniques and keys to convert plaintext into cipher text. AI can contribute to encryption by making several components of the process better, including:

1. **Key generation:** By studying patterns and creating complicated, hard-to-guess sequences, AI algorithms can help create strong encryption keys.
2. **Cryptography algorithms:** AI can help with the creation and improvement of cryptography algorithms. Machine learning techniques can be used to find and fix weaknesses in already-existing algorithms or to develop completely new ones.
3. **Threat detection:** AI can help identify potential threats to encrypted data, such as brute-force attacks or pattern recognition attacks. By monitoring network traffic or analysing system logs, AI algorithms can detect anomalous behaviour and trigger additional encryption measures.
4. **Quantum encryption:** As quantum computing develops, current encryption techniques may become insecure. Artificial intelligence (AI) can be utilized to create and employ quantum encryption methods that can fend off attacks from quantum computers.
5. **Encrypted data is sent securely thanks to AI algorithms that can examine communication channels for potential weaknesses.** These algorithms are capable of identifying secure protocols, keeping an eye on network activity, and discouraging illegal access.

It is crucial to remember that when combined with reliable key management procedures and powerful encryption algorithms. AI can increase the security and effectiveness of encryption procedures; it is not a replacement for current encryption techniques.

C. *IP(Internet Protocol) Address*

Each device connected to a computer network that employs the Internet Protocol is given a unique numerical label known as an IP (Internet Protocol) address. It accomplishes two major tasks: locating the device within the network and identifying the host or network interface. IP addresses come in two flavours: IPv4 (such as 192.168.1.1) and IPv6 (such as 2001:0db8:85a3:0000:0000:8a2e:0370:7334). IPv6 was created to solve IPv4's shortcomings as a result of the increasing number of devices connecting to the internet.

D. *IPwith Encryption*

To increase security during transmission, IP signals—the data packets sent over the Internet Protocol—can be encrypted and decrypted. Data that has been encrypted before transmission is converted into a ciphertext that cannot be decrypted without the decryption key. The only person who has the decryption key and can turn the ciphertext back into the original plaintext is the intended recipient.

Sensitive data must be protected from unauthorized access via encryption and decryption of IP signals, especially when the data is delivered across open networks like the internet. This procedure makes sure that even if the data packets are intercepted, the content cannot be decoded without the right decryption key. For this purpose, SSL/TLS for secure web communication and VPNs for encrypted networks are frequently used encryption methods.

A proactive strategy for improving cyber security involves integrating AI with encryption and a hack alarm system. Here is a general description of how this may function:

1. **Data Encryption:** Protect sensitive data before it is stored or transmitted by the AI. This guarantees that the data will be protected even in the event of unwanted access.
2. **Real-time observation** Set up ongoing system log and network traffic monitoring, as well as AI operations. By analysing trends and abnormalities, AI systems can be utilized to spot potential attacks or unauthorized access.
3. **Intrusion Detection:** Educate AI models to identify indicators of unauthorized access or peculiar behaviour. This could involve rapid surges in data traffic, erroneous logon habits, or unexpected data requests.
4. **The hacker alert system:** The AI raises an alert when it discovers a potential hack or incursion. Real-time delivery of this alert is possible to administrators or a security team.
5. **Response Automation:** Automate replies to specific alerts by implementing response automation. For instance, the system may automatically disconnect the impacted component from the network or start more security measures if a specific sort of hack is discovered.
6. **Machine learning for adaptation:** Educate AI models to take lessons from previous breaches and modify their detection methods accordingly. As a result, the system improves over time at spotting novel and developing hacking approaches.
7. **Key Management for Encryption:** Manage the encryption keys needed to protect data properly. To prevent theft, rotate your keys frequently and make sure they're kept safely.
8. **Collaborate with Security Teams:** Integrate the AI-based hack alarm system with the current resources and procedures used by your security team. Making judgments in difficult conditions requires human scrutiny.
9. **Continuous Updates:** To stay ahead of any weaknesses, keep the AI system updated with the newest security updates and enhancements.

Although AI can significantly improve cyber security efforts, it cannot replace a comprehensive security plan. The best defense against hackers and breaches is a layered strategy that combines AI with well-known security procedures.

E. *Changing the data from one IP to another IP*

Following a malware alert, you can take the following actions to encrypt data by utilizing AI to pass it from one IP address to another IP address:

1. **Choose a reliable and safe AI-enabled encryption technique:** Look for well-established encryption frameworks or algorithms that encrypt data using artificial intelligence (AI) techniques like neural networks. This can include methods like encryption based on deep learning or cryptographic protocols created especially for AI applications.
2. **Install and set up encryption software:** Install the selected encryption program on both the source IP address, from which the data is coming, and the destination IP address, to which you wish to send the data securely. To configure the software properly, abide by any instructions or documentation that have been provided.

3. Specify the encryption parameters, such as the encryption strength (for example, AES-256) and mode of operation (for example, CBC, GCM).
4. Establish a secure connection: Ensure that the source and destination IP addresses have a secure network connection. This could entail employing secure VPN tunnels or adopting secure protocols like SSL/TLS.
5. Encrypt the data: At the source IP address, encrypt the data using encryption software that supports AI. Set the software up to utilize the specified encryption settings.
6. Send the encrypted data: Using the created secure connection, send the encrypted data from the source IP address to the destination IP address. Utilizing secure file transfer protocols like SFTP or SCP may be required for this.
7. decode the data at the destination IP address: At the destination IP address, use the same AI-enabled encryption program to decode the encrypted data you've just received. Set the software up using the same encryption parameters as were used for encryption.
8. Check data integrity: After decryption, check the data's integrity to make sure it wasn't altered in transit. Digital signatures or a comparison of cryptographic hash values can be used for this.
9. Handle encrypted data securely: After the data has been decrypted, make sure it is handled safely and is not exposed to any potential malware or dangers. Implement suitable security measures, such as safe storage, access controls, and frequent virus scans.

IV. INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY SECURITY

Security in Information and Communication Technology (ICT) is about securing the specific technology-based systems in which information is typically stored and/or transferred. The international standard describes ICT protection as all aspects of the confidentiality, honesty, availability, non-repudiation, transparency, accuracy and reliability of information resources. Because information security requires the defense of the information resources underlying it, it can be argued that ICT security is a sub-component of information security.

Consequently, the concept of ICT security is somewhat close to that of information security. However, additional characteristics are added to the description, which could be best defined in this context as services which should be provided by secure information resources. Including non-repudiation, transparency, honesty and reliability, the principle of data security is often referred to as denoting the defense of real data in the information system. Since the definition given in Dhillon includes most of the characteristics in the definition of IT security, and since the security of the underlying data is largely dependent on the overall protection of the information system on which the data resides,, it can be argued that the term data security is in fact used in Dhillon to refer to the same concept as that which ISO/IEC TR 13335-1 calls ICT security.

This should be evident from the meanings addressed that there is a distinction between securing the resources for information and securing ICT resources. A safe resource for information may include any organization from which information is obtained or to which it is sent. A secure resource for information technology is a protected repository of information that happens to reside on an IT network. It is also necessary to remember that information alone cannot be considered protected in terms of ICT-based systems unless all of the tools and processes that deal with that information are also protected.

As mentioned above, the first three attributes, confidentiality, honesty and availability, are widely referred to as the CIA triangle model, which since the introduction of the mainframe has been considered the industry standard for computer security. In today's inter-networked business setting, new elements have been added to the concept to meet the security needs of organizations. A clear understanding of the meaning of all of the above is essential for an understanding of information and ICT security, as without the confidentiality, integrity, availability, non-repudiation, accountability, authenticity and reliability of the information. All of the above (including the precision, utility and possession of information) play an important role in the security of information and should be considered equally relevant. However, one or more of these characteristics or services may, depending on the nature of the information itself, be more applicable in specific scenarios than other. For example, the accuracy of inflationary statistics is of obvious interest to economists, although the confidentiality of the same data seems to be unimportant because it would certainly allow anyone to access such information.

However, by definition a violation of confidentiality happens only if the information is accessed by an unauthorized party. In this scenario, because everybody would be an authorized recipient of inflationary data, the confidentiality of the information would in effect be maintained. Therefore, maintaining the protection of the information of the organization in an organizational sense is not a case of determining the features or services are appropriate, but rather of correctly identifying the permitted entities and other criteria for any given piece of information. As described above, when analyzing ICT security, it is clear that various threats target related vulnerabilities, and ultimately have a negative impact on ICT infrastructure. It is obvious in this case that the technical infrastructure is considered to be the asset which requires protection. Accordingly, ICT is the asset that is protected in ICT

security.

In the case of information security, ICT is the system where information is collected, stored and communicated. In this case, it is a knowledge which is considered to be the asset which requires security.

V. CONCLUSION

It examined the meanings of both the security of information and ICT. Also argued that cyber security is distinct from information security, despite sometimes being used as an equivalent concept for information security. Information security is information defense, which is an advantage, against potential harm resulting from various threats and vulnerabilities. At the other hand, cyber security is not only the defense of cyberspace itself, but also the safety of those operating in cyberspace, and all of their properties that can be accessed via cyberspace. This paper argues that while cyber security and information protection are significantly similar, these two terms are not exactly comparable. In addition, the paper argues that cyber security reaches beyond conventional information security boundaries to include not only the protection of information resources, but also that of other properties, including the individual himself. In information protection, reference to the human factor is generally linked to human's role(s) in the process of protection. In cyber security this aspect has a further element, namely, humans as possible targets of cyber-attacks or even engaging unknowingly in a cyber-assault.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] M. M. Yamin, B. Katt, and V. Gkioulos, "Cyber ranges and security testbeds: Scenarios, functions, tools and architecture," *Computers and Security*. 2020.
- [2] M. A. Khan and K. Salah, "IoT security: Review, blockchain solutions, and open challenges," *Futur. Gener. Comput. Syst.*, 2018.
- [3] C. Lee, H. Bin Yim, and P. H. Seong, "Development of a quantitative method for evaluating the efficacy of cyber security controls in NPPs based on intrusion tolerant concept," *Ann. Nucl. Energy*, 2018.
- [4] J. Srinivas, A. K. Das, and N. Kumar, "Government regulations in cyber security: Framework, standards and recommendations," *Futur. Gener. Comput. Syst.*, 2019.
- [5] I. M. Venter, R. J. Blignaut, K. Renaud, and M. A. Venter, "Cyber security education is as essential as 'the three R's,'" *Heliyon*, 2019.
- [6] K. F. Cheung and M. G. H. Bell, "Attacker-defender model against quantal response adversaries for cyber security in logistics management: An introductory study," *Eur. J. Oper. Res.*, 2019.
- [7] M. A. Ferrag, L. Maglaras, S. Moschoyiannis, and H. Janicke, "Deep learning for cyber security intrusion detection: Approaches, datasets, and comparative study," *J. Inf. Secur. Appl.*, 2020.
- [8] R. Vinayakumar, M. Alazab, K. P. Soman, P. Poornachandran, A. Al-Nemrat, and S. Venkatraman, "Deep Learning Approach for Intelligent Intrusion Detection System," *IEEE Access*, 2019.
- [9] Y. Yu, J. Long, and Z. Cai, "Network Intrusion Detection through Stacking Dilated Convolutional Autoencoders," *Secur. Commun. Networks*, 2017.
- [10] Yan, D. Jin, C. W. Lee, and P. Liu, "A Comparative Study of Off-Line Deep Learning Based Network Intrusion Detection," in *International Conference on Ubiquitous and Future Networks, ICUFN*, 2018.